

The interdisciplinary infrastructure of explainability: XAI stakeholders, tools and approaches: two empirical case studies from the FinTech industry.

Wojtek Buczynski

University of Cambridge; London Business School; Fast Audit AI; FirmView AI; wb292@cam.ac.uk

Jingkun (Charly) Zhu

King's College London; Tsinghua University; Fast Audit AI; FirmView AI; charly.zhu@fastaudit.ai

Explainable AI is not a new concept[10]. Explainability has also been central to financial services at least since the 2008 financial crisis. It is a pragmatic, reputational as well as oftentimes regulatory requirement.

Explainable AI has been a longstanding concern in financial services, but LLM-based agents reshape the problem: explainability must cover not only model outputs, but also multi-step tool use, evidence selection, and conflict resolution across an agent trajectory.

Leveraging our interdisciplinary experience as finance industry professionals, academic researchers of computer science and AI regulations, and, most recently, AI FinTech startup founders, our paper will discuss the complete XAI infrastructure – stakeholders, tools, workflows, regulatory considerations – based on two real-world use cases our startups are addressing.

Our contributions to the workshop will be:

1. Real-world XAI approaches, tools and workflows developed and implemented in our two startups.
2. A comprehensive discussion of XAI stakeholders: their needs, objectives and constraints in two real-world use cases.
3. Wider discussion on trust, accountability and explainability from the perspective of high-stakes, highly regulated industry that is financial services.

CCS CONCEPTS • Human-centered computing → Human computer interaction (HCI) → HCI design and evaluation methods; Interactive systems and tools.

KEYWORDS: Artificial Intelligence (AI), agentic AI, Large Language Models (LLMs), human-computer interaction (HCI), financial services, audit, explainability infrastructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Financial services have long been at the forefront of adoption of modern technologies: it is one of the most data-intensive industries – as well as the most fiercely competitive ones. Data and technology can make the difference between profit and loss; between a competitive edge and lack thereof.

The challenges of explainable AI first became salient when high-performing models such as deep neural networks and gradient-boosted ensembles turned out to be “black boxes”: they may produce correct results and they have the potential to add value, yet their “opacity” – and thus inexplicability – makes their use risky – potentially unacceptably risky – from the regulatory and risk management perspectives. In response, financial teams constrained ML to “contained” use cases with human oversight and adopted post-hoc tools such as SHAP and counterfactual explanations to support review.

LLM-based agents enable open-ended ingestions and synthesis of heterogeneous qualitative and quantitative information. This expands the space of high-stakes applications, but it also raises new explainability requirements: what evidence was used, which tools were called, why specific sources were trusted, and how uncertainty and conflicts were handled.

With the arrival of LLMs and agentic AI decades-old specialist roles and hierarchies have suddenly found themselves “in flux” and vulnerable to disruption by the very technology they are trying to leverage. Finance professionals are highly paid, and financial firms are always keen on cost savings – the vision of replacing a professional earning hundred(s) of thousands of dollars with an AI agent is understandably tempting.

Hallucinations, however, remain a central barrier in high-stakes deployment. While retrieval, tool use, and draft–verify style checks reduce errors through evidence gathering[5], tool-using such as search and API calls[8], self-supervised tool learning[9], as well as explicit draft–verify loops for self-checking[1, 6, 7], survey evidence suggests hallucinations persist across prompting, long-form generation, and tool-augmented regimes, which makes ‘explicit grounding + verification’ a design requirement rather than an optional enhancement[4].

Given both the regulatory onus as well as reputational downside, transparency and explainability has been a central consideration in financial services, particularly post-2008 great financial crisis. It is a topic financial services are arguably well-versed in. Consequently, there is an existing “explainability infrastructure” in the industry we can learn from and build on.

Financial services are therefore a fascinating case study in challenges and opportunities for explainability in the era of agentic AI: a “data hungry” industry always on the lookout for informational and analytical edge over the competition on one side; and a huge reputational and regulatory downside should something go wrong on the other.

Human stakeholders are central to this debate (at the very least, for regulatory and risk management reasons). There are various “explainability stakeholders” within financial firms, bound by different covenants – including but not limited to business, technology, regulation and compliance – and we can yield valuable insights from their diverse perspectives.

We first talked about the fundamental importance of transparency and explainability pre-LLM era[11], and we made further points from the regulatory perspective in our subsequent papers[12, 13]. Then we started building on our academic and industry experience in our two agentic AI FinTech startups – Fast Audit AI and FirmView AI. As a result, we bring an interdisciplinary academic-pragmatic perspective and approach to the ongoing XAI debate.

2 HCTXAI IN PRACTICE – CASE STUDIES

2.1 Financial audit

Audit, in its nature, is not exceptionally difficult intellectually. It is, however, exceptionally laborious, increasingly complex – and, importantly, it has not changed much in decades. While screens and spreadsheets have replaced paper financial statements, audit remains largely about looking at numbers, analysing them, and reconciling them. Over the years, as the size and complexity of business has been growing, so has complexity of the audits – as well as their costs, which have been rising at astonishing rates[3].

One of our startups – Fast Audit AI – is focused on a specific task called anomaly detection or in other words: finding numbers that do not fit. Anomaly detection is all about detecting patterns and then outliers to these patterns – it is a task Machine Learning seems ideally suited to; which it is. The core anomaly detection system is a combination of rules-based and Machine Learning algorithms.

The challenge is that identifying an outlier is of limited value to the auditors – without context, without explanation, without knowing “why is this an outlier?” there is little they can do with this insight. This is exactly where LLMs can add substantial value – they can provide context and / or offer some plausible, factual explanations as to why a given number is what it is – and particularly, whether the cause may be perfectly legitimate; or whether this is something that needs to be investigated thoroughly as potential wrongdoing. Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) can improve grounding, but it does not by itself guarantee factual correctness, especially when evidence is weakly supportive, stale, or inconsistently retrieved—hence the need for explicit evidence constraints and verification gates. This creates a seemingly irreconcilable friction between the stakeholders: the auditors, the audit oversight bodies (Financial Reporting Council in the UK) and us, the AI vendors such as Fast Audit.

Crucially, audit industry requires utmost transparency, auditability and explainability – those are the core tenets of the role of the auditor.

Can this conundrum be resolved somehow? We developed a couple of ideas; importantly, they are not purely technological – the fundamental part of our approach is human-centricity, auditability and transparency.

Instead of relying on model choice alone, we operationalise auditability via Atomic Evidence Packs (AEPs): every tool result or derived computation that can influence the final answer is captured as a minimal, immutable evidence unit with provenance (source identifier, retrieval parameters, timestamp, tool/agent version) and a journey trace of how it was produced. AEPs are not merely stored references; they act as control objects—downstream steps must cite AEP ids when making claims, enabling automated supportiveness checks and structured human review. Over a task, the AEP set forms an evidence graph with explicit support/contradiction links, so disagreements are represented as competing subgraphs rather than being silently resolved inside a latent chain-of-thought.

Next, we moved away from a “standalone” LLM approach toward a combined LLM + agentic workflow. We then adopted a planner-centric orchestration layer: a Planner decomposes a task and routes it to specialised nodes. Tool nodes (e.g., search/crawl, long-document reader, reconciliation/reranking) produce schema-constrained outputs that are converted into AEPs; a Writer node synthesizes the final response strictly from the evidence bundle and can reject the bundle when evidence is insufficient or contradictory, returning a structured critique to the Planner.

The system is coordinated by a Planner agent that produces an explicit, executable next-step decision, following the broader “plan–execute” and “planner–executor” separation that has been shown to improve controllability and efficiency in tool-augmented

LLM systems. With LLM as agentic AI's orchestrator, evaluator and supervisor we discovered a simple way to manage a number of AI agents within a single, unified process.

In high-stakes finance workflows with little to no margin for error, we do not rely on the agent alone to control hallucinations, because small factual errors can compound across steps. We therefore adopt a tiered review policy: (i) for numeric facts and extracted financial data (e.g., values, units/currency, periods), human verification is mandatory; (ii) for templated narrative completion where the outline and evidence are fixed, we use spot checks; and (iii) for consequential analytic claims, we require full human read-through. To reduce reviewer burden, we additionally use a cheaper verifier model to flag inconsistencies for human escalation.

The entire system is "packaged" into a user-facing chatbot we called Charly – "Charly the chatbot" aka CtC – which was added to the existing, Machine Learning-based anomaly detection system. This made the ultimate synergy: quantitative analysis of financial statements augmented by qualitative insights from CtC. CtC is designed not to give definitive statements (something conventional LLMs are very good at, even if they're confabulating) and to speak in terms of what could be the likely explanation. Furthermore, we tried to make it so that whenever possible CtC presents a range of plausible explanations. This "inconclusivity" is important when auditors are the key stakeholders. Auditors need to retain their intellectual autonomy and professional judgment – fundamental tenets of their industry – with our solution positioned as an analytical support tool.

Through the abovementioned organic, highly iterative process, we were able to "open the black box" (or at least peer inside it) and dramatically increase veracity, auditability, transparency and explainability of the agentic LLM whilst preserving the immense added value of agentic AI to the audit process. Notably, the entire process is human-centric: we provided solutions, checks and balances specifically with the end-users (auditors) in mind: their needs, goals and constraints. The other set of stakeholders is of course the technical staff inside Fast Audit AI – and interestingly, their explainability needs match those of the end-users.

Lastly, there are two important outcomes from the perspective of explainability:

- i. There is a full audit trail of the agentic AI discussions and "negotiations" with the LLM for Fast Audit AI – we can see fine-tune the system on ongoing basis.
- ii. We log the execution trace (plans, tool calls, node outputs) and the AEP evidence graph, so reviewers can reconstruct which evidence and transformations led to each claim in the final response. Rather than treating a model's chain-of-thought as an explanation, we ground user-facing rationales in inspectable evidence objects and recorded decisions, enabling post-hoc review, contestation, and selective escalation to human auditors when evidence is weak or conflicting.

2.2 Equity analysis

Equity research is a fundamental part of the investment industry – it is also tightly regulated. It serves two main purposes:

- i. It provides a snapshot of the current situation of the covered company including all material information, developments and financial performance, prepared by an expert analyst.
- ii. It provides share price forecast for a fixed time horizon (usually 6 – 12 months) along with a simple recommendation: Buy, Sell or Hold.

Typically, a research report is a combination of free-form text and financial data. It is the analyst's personal judgment to decide what information they consider material and relevant. The price forecast is the ultimate expression of the analyst's judgement and should be a logical conclusion of the facts, numbers and opinions included in the report.

In our equity analysis startup – FirmView AI – we found four practical use cases for agentic LLMs in investment workflows: (1) automated news aggregation on companies and geopolitical context; (2) automated aggregation of user/consumer reviews and commentary; (3) semi-automated financial data collection from trusted sources; and (4) semi-automated investment research generation. In this submission we focus on (3) and (4), because they demand the strongest auditability, provenance, and human review policies. (3) and (4) are perfect use cases to utilise LLM + agentic AI combo. Information that can be material and have impact on a company's performance, and, by extension, on its share price is vast, unbounded and heterogenous. It could be general economic and market developments (global or local); it could be industry-specific impacts; it could be political or regulatory developments; lastly it could be random, unforeseeable events like Covid. While research reports and financial statements tend to be highly structured and orderly, the starting point is subjective information sourcing, data selection and filtering. Historically, this has always been a domain of human analysts – highly-paid professionals who honed their talents and instincts through years of practice. As the job has a degree of subjectivity and judgement call, it has been considered highly "cerebral" and generally safe from AI disruption. Then came LLMs, followed by agentic AI, and they started to change everything.

Evidence scope and release controls are central in this domain. In our current production workflow, externally verifiable evidence for research reports is restricted to primary sources: company filings/financial statements and the covered company's official website. Financial data collection (use case 3) produces candidate evidence items that require human evaluation before they are admitted into

our internal evidence store; research generation (use case 4) is then constrained to cite and compose only from these approved evidence items, resorting to targeted web retrieval only to fill clearly identified gaps within the same primary-source scope.

LLMs can produce professional-looking equity research, but without strict evidence control such reports risk being factually incorrect (hallucinated) or otherwise useless (“AI slop”). Finance professionals recognise that such reports have little or no value, and require thorough proof-reading and fact-checking from an expert, which defeats their purpose. With all the data available online it is possible to arrive at new, original insights – so the tool is not misplaced, and the use case does make sense; it just needs very thoughtful workflow design.

Two design decisions emerged early through iteration. First, we moved away from a “standalone” LLM approach toward a combined LLM + agentic workflow, which produced immediate improvements in scope and depth by decomposing work into tool-using subtasks. Second, we found that whether the user interacts with a live system (chat-like) versus a static artifact (a report) fundamentally changes the risk profile and control strategy. Static report generation enables explicit verification gates and a final expert review before release, which in turn makes it feasible to reduce unsupported claims below the workflow’s release threshold.

Because unsupported claims and small numeric errors can compound across multi-step pipelines, we do not treat “model self-checking”, sometimes effective for less critical use cases, as sufficient. Instead, we enforce verification gates: (i) automated supportiveness checks for whether cited evidence actually supports a claim (ii) lightweight cross-checks for high-risk numeric fields; and (iii) mandatory expert review at release time for the static report artifact. This design follows the broader trend of draft–verify loops while recognising that regulated workflows require explicit documentation and logging for post-hoc inspection.

When multiple sources disagree (common in finance due to reporting conventions, currencies, and revisions), we represent support/contradiction relations explicitly as typed edges between AEPs, rather than silently resolving conflicts inside the model. Conceptually this aligns with bipolar argumentation structures and recent retrieval-plus-argumentation directions for contestable verification. The practical benefit is stakeholder-facing: compliance can see what evidence was competing, business can see what was chosen and why, and engineers can debug failure points.

We also designed an agentic auditing assistant whose primary technical objective is auditability: the ability to reconstruct, inspect, and contest how a final answer was produced. Concretely, every intermediate step that can influence the final answer—retrieval results, tool outputs, derived computations, and conflict resolution decisions—is captured as an AEP. AEPs are accumulated into an evidence set that is reused across turns in the same conversation; in future work, the set can be upgraded into a vector-indexed evidence store, aligning with the standard RAG pattern of maintaining a non-parametric memory that can be updated without retraining. In addition to being a storage object, an AEP is also a control object: subsequent reasoning steps must explicitly (i) cite AEP ids when making claims, and (ii) optionally attach quote-level anchors where the modality permits (text passages, document extracts). This is motivated by evidence-grounded systems that emphasize quote-ability and reproducibility as part of the evidence interface.

In our workflow design – evidence capture, conflict handling, review gates – explainability is the core consideration. Externally cited evidence is restricted to company filings and the target company’s official website; most facts are retrieved from our internal database as pre-built AEPs, and targeted web retrieval is only triggered to fill explicit evidence gaps. This keeps provenance tight while still enabling semi-automated report drafting under human review gates. All outputs from AI agents for equity analysis are being logged and they are reviewed – alongside the final, proposed report content – by a human analyst. Given the static nature of equity research reports and the severe downside of allowing any hallucinated inputs we put human in the loop at various stages of the equity report generation – chief among them being the final approval.

Specifically, we design robust workflows with technical quality controls and humans-in-the-loop, prioritizing explainability and auditability: reducing unsupported claims (hallucinations) during generation and enforcing explicit verification and expert review before release.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Having discussed AI agents in great detail above, we would now like to focus on their human counterparts. Different stakeholders – technology, business, compliance, management – may be expected to have different explainability needs. However – based on the two use cases above, as well as our academic research and industry experience – we learn that, at least within financial services, those needs seem to revolve around the same core tenets:

- i. Full source information.
- ii. Factual correctness (veracity), completeness and timeliness.
- iii. Evidence / decision trace.

Different stakeholders may consume this information in very different ways, and from different angles: for example, for Fast Audit's and FirmView's engineers it can be "could we have found more / better insights?" or "could the agentic system have delivered the results at lower compute cost?"; while for a compliance end-user in an investment firm it could be "are there any EU AI Act considerations to address?". Domain-specificity plays a big part here, because business or compliance users will likely want to see AI's chain of reasoning presented as a "chain of thought" narrative they could scrutinize and evaluate; while an AI engineer may be interested in a much more technical, algorithmic kind of reasoning. However, the abovementioned core tenets appear to be central and universal across various stakeholders and use cases. This raises an interesting question for future debate and research: how different are explainability needs of AI users across various industries and professional roles?

Another interesting question is that of excusable vs. explainable AI. While AI – agentic or otherwise – is an increasingly complex and nuanced consideration within financial services, the answer to this question comes as surprisingly unambiguous based on our first-hand industry experience: the latter. Even if the industry could try to argue that a less-than-transparent AI system is acceptable from the regulatory perspective – which would be a difficult argument to defend in our view – it is quite likely that such system would be deemed too risky internally, from the perspective of risk management, reputation and common sense. If we wanted to nuance this discussion, we could argue that AI regulation – and thus practice – is based on the principle of proportionality, which is explicitly stated in the EU AI Act. Consequently, there may be degrees of AI explainability, which is correct – not all modern-day AI systems can be 100% explainable. However, we would argue that both regulators as well as financial organizations themselves set the bar relatively high for risk management, customer protection and market integrity reasons, and "excusability" may not meet it. We think that – for IP and legal reasons – financial organizations may be sometimes reluctant to *disclose* full explainability record – but that is very different to not having it in the first place.

Just like explainability itself, the issue of accountability is long-established in financial services. In some jurisdictions – such as for example UK, where there is Senior Managers and Certification Regime, SM&CR – it is explicitly embedded in regulatory framework; in others, even in the absence of an explicit regulation, regulators may still be able to sanction senior managers. Consequently, clear delineation of accountability becomes a fundamental, non-negotiable consideration. This, in turn, informs both autonomy granted to agentic AI vis-à-vis its human operators as well as explainability itself. One could argue that these considerations could even explain the limited observable impact of AI on the financial services industry to date.

Explainability, accountability and autonomy of agentic AI ultimately link to regulation: both finance-specific (such as Markets in Financial Instruments Directive 2014/65/EU [MIFID II]) and sector-neutral AI regulation. Many European enterprises – for-profit and public services – will to some extent fall under the aegis of the EU AI Act[2]. Even if they do not fall under the category of explicitly regulated high-risk AI systems, they will fall under the "catch-all" Article 95, which covers *"drawing up of codes of conduct, including related governance mechanisms, intended to foster the voluntary application to AI systems, other than high-risk AI systems, of some or all of the requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2 taking into account the available technical solutions and industry best practices allowing for the application of such requirements"*. We interpret Article 95 as a *de facto* requirement to implement most provisions of the act in a flexible, proportionate manner – with national and sectoral regulators deciding whether individual firms have implemented those – technically non-binding – best practices to their satisfaction.

Finally, there is the key question of whether AI – agentic or otherwise – should be regarded as "hostile" competition or beneficial enhancement / augmentation by its human users. This is neither an academic nor a philosophical question – it's a question that directly informs the level of autonomy given to AI / retained by humans as well as the nature of human-AI interactions. As regards defining the nature of the relationship between humans and LLMs, we frame the workflow as a bounded, asymmetric form of interdependence. Humans depend on the system for scalable evidence triage, synthesis, and rapid iteration across heterogeneous sources, while the system depends on humans for goal specification, risk-sensitive judgment, and final accountability under regulated constraints. In high-stakes financial settings, this interdependence is deliberately structured through auditable artifacts, explicit conflict representations, and verification gates that allocate control and responsibility to the appropriate stakeholders at each stage. We consider the antagonistic approach ("humans vs AI") as suboptimal to the collaborative one ("humans and AI"); we first wrote about it years ago[11] and we have only solidified our convictions since.

The final observation we would like to share with the workshop community is also the most vulnerable one. We presented two use cases from the same industry. They are not very closely linked but share the fundamental underlying technologies (LLMs + agentic AI; or, as we call them, "agentic LLMs"). Yet, even within the same industry, and very similar tech stack, we documented multiple use case-specific considerations, both in terms of workflows as well as the nuances of how technology is deployed, where the potential "points of failure" are, what the right place(s) to put "humans in the loop" are etc. As much as we would like to present a single focused position, both our academic and venture experiences indicate otherwise: each use case is unique and different. Instead of abovementioned position we share observations and lessons learned which in our view are universal and "generalize-able" enough to

be of value to the broader HCXAI community regardless of what industry or sector they work in. We think that the fact that we implemented them in real-world, client-facing solutions made our insights grounded and practical. We presented a number of considerations that can be used as “building blocks” (or at least “prompts”) for HCXAI frameworks across various industries, both for-profit and otherwise. We look forward to continuing our contributions to this fascinating area both on practical (business) as well as academic fronts and hope to be able to share our insights with the workshop participants.

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